

NOTES

Aspartate Complexes of Cobalt-, Nickel-, Copper- and Zinc-(II)

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ASPARTIC acid (α -aminosuccinic acid) is readily synthesised in the animal body. Its role in chelation and transportation of trace metal ions in the biological system is being investigated. Literature reports the formation of several 1:1 and 1:2 aspartate complexes¹. We present here the formation of neutral aspartate complexes at lower pH and their dissociation to anionic complexes at higher pH by a different pH-metric method.

Experimental

Three sets of experiments were carried out at $30 \pm 1^\circ$ under nitrogen atmosphere and at ionic strength of 0.1 M (KNO_3) using ECI-8224 pH meter. A Vax 11/780 computer with a suitable programme was used to calculate the formation constants.

Results and Discussion

The isoelectric pH of aspartic acid is 3.0, hence around this pH it is likely to be present as zwitterion.

In the 1:1 metal-ligand ratio (Fig. 1) the reactions can be represented as

where C is the complex formed and n is the number of protons liberated per g-atom of metal ion. The values of n were calculated² according to the equations (2), by using dissociation constant k_1 , k_2 and k_3 values of aspartic acid³ as 1.148×10^{-2} , 2.138×10^{-4} and 2.398×10^{-10} respectively.

$$\frac{\Delta[\text{NaOH}] - a/b \Delta[\text{T Asp}]}{[\text{C}]} = n - \frac{a}{b} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 1. pH-titration of 100 ml of solution containing (A) 1×10^{-2} g-mol KNO_3 and 6.25×10^{-4} g-mol aspartic acid, (B₁-B₄) 5×10^{-4} g-mol $\text{Co}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$, ZnSO_4 , NiSO_4 and CuSO_4 respectively, besides the same constituents as in (A).

where, $a = \frac{k_2}{[\text{H}^+]} + 2 \frac{k_2 k_3}{[\text{H}^+]^2} - \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k_1}$ and

$$b = 1 + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k_1} + \frac{k_2}{[\text{H}^+]} + \frac{k_2 k_3}{[\text{H}^+]^2}$$

The values of n are less than 2 below pH 7.60, 6.10, 5.10 and 7.40 for Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} aspartate systems respectively. Assuming n to be 2 below these pH, the equilibrium constants (K) for reaction (3),

were calculated (Table 1).

In the pH ranges of 7.6-9.04, 6.1-9.0, 5.1-7.0 and 7.4-7.90 for Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} aspartate systems respectively, the values of n are greater than 2 but less than 3. Hence in these pH ranges the complex C dissociates to C_1^- and a proton,

The equilibrium constants (K_1) for reaction (4) have been calculated³ and are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF 1:1 AND 1:2 TRANSITION METAL-ASPARTATE COMPLEXES AT $30 \pm 1^\circ$ AND AT IONIC STRENGTH OF 0.1 M (KNO_3)

Cation	1:1 complex (Fig. 1)		1:2 complexes		$-\log (K_2 \times k_2)$
	$-\log K$	$-\log K_1$	$-\log K_{1:2}$ (Fig. 2)	$-\log K_2$ (Fig. 3)	
Co^{II}	7.34 ± 0.01	8.83 ± 0.07	16.47 ± 0.23	3.83 ± 0.04	7.49
Ni^{II}	6.15 ± 0.07	7.71 ± 0.05	14.54 ± 0.31	2.72 ± 0.05	6.39
Cu^{II}	4.76 ± 0.11	6.74 ± 0.09	11.55 ± 0.30	1.14 ± 0.03	4.81
Zn^{II}	7.35 ± 0.02	8.71 ± 0.09	16.50 ± 0.28	3.95 ± 0.02	7.62

Precipitation occurred at pH 9.04, 9.00, 7.00 and 7.90 for Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} aspartate systems respectively.

Fig. 2. pH titration curves: (A) 1×10^{-3} g-mol KNO_3 and 1.25×10^{-3} g-mol aspartic acid, (B₁-B₄) 5×10^{-4} g-mol $\text{Co}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$, ZnSO_4 , NiSO_4 and CuSO_4 respectively, besides the same constituents as in (A).

Formation of 1 : 2 metal-aspartate complexes :

The reaction taking place in the formation of 1 : 2 aspartate complexes can be represented as

The values of n were calculated⁴ from equation (6),

$$\frac{\Delta[\text{NaOH}] - a/b \Delta[\text{T Asp}]}{[\text{C}]} = n - 2a/b \quad (6)$$

The values of n are less than 4 in all these systems. Assuming the values of n to be 4, the equilibrium constant ($K_{1:2}$) for the reaction, $\text{M}^{2+} + 2\text{H}_2 \text{Asp} \rightleftharpoons \text{C}_{1:2} + 4\text{H}^+$ have been calculated (Table 1).

The reaction due to the addition of monosodium aspartate to the metal ion (Fig. 3) can be represented as

Fig. 3. pH titration curve: (A) 1×10^{-3} g-mol KNO_3 , (B₁-B₄) 5×10^{-4} g-mol $\text{Co}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$, ZnSO_4 , NiSO_4 and CuSO_4 respectively, besides the same constituents as in (A).

It has been observed from experiment 1 that the complex C exists in the pH range of this experiment (below 1 : 1 metal-ligand ratio). The equilibrium

constants (K_s) for reaction (7) were calculated as before by using the equations,

$$[\text{T H}_2 \text{Asp}] = p [\text{H Asp}^-] + [\text{C}] \quad (8)$$

$$[\text{C}] = [\text{H}^+] + r [\text{H Asp}^-] \quad (9)$$

$$\text{and } [\text{T H}_2 \text{Asp}] = [\text{H}^+] + [\text{H Asp}^-] (p+r) \quad (10)$$

where, $p = 1 + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k_2} + \frac{k_3}{[\text{H}^+]} + \frac{[\text{H}^+]^2}{k_1 k_2}$;

$$r = \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k_2} + \frac{2[\text{H}^+]^2}{k_1 k_2} - \frac{k_3}{[\text{H}^+]}$$

and are recorded in Table 1.

It can be shown that $K = K_s \times k_2$. The values of K thus calculated by substituting the values of K_s and k_2 in the above relation, are recorded in Table 1, which are similar to the values of K calculated in experiment 1.

The relative order of stability of these metal-aspartate complexes at lower pH ranges was found to be $\text{Cu}^{II} > \text{Ni}^{II} > \text{Co}^{II} > \text{Zn}^{II}$. However, at higher pH ranges the Zn complexes were found to be a little more stable than the Co complexes.

Aspartic acid coordinates to the metal ions through two carboxyl groups and an amino group for the formation of neutral complexes. A proton from the coordinated water molecules may be dissociating for the formation of anionic complexes.

References

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Polymetallic Complexes. Part-XIII. Iron-, Cobalt-, Nickel-, Copper-, Zinc- and Mercury-(II) Complexes with ONO Tridentate Schiff Bases

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A series of metal complexes containing salicylidene amino acids as ligands have been reported by Ray and Mukherjee¹. Dutta and Bhattacharya² prepared mixed chelates of salicylidene aminoacids and bidentate nitrogen donors². The present paper describes the synthesis of two dibasic ONO tridentate Schiff bases, acetophenone glycine and acetophenone alanine, and their complexation behaviour with Fe^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} and Hg^{II} .